

Correlation analysis of reactivity in the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by 2,2'-bipyridinium chlorochromate

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Abstract : Oxidation of benzyl alcohol and some *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-monosubstituted ones by 2,2'-bipyridinium chlorochromate (BPCC) in DMSO leads to the formation of corresponding benzaldehydes. The reaction is first order in both BPCC and the alcohol. The reaction is promoted by hydrogen ions; the hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. Oxidation of α,α -dideuteriobenzyl alcohol (PhCD_2OH) has exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.60$ at 298 K). The reaction has been studied in nineteen organic solvents and the effect of solvent analysed using Taft's and Swain's multi-parametric equations. The rates of oxidation of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzyl alcohols have been correlated in terms of Charton's triparametric LDR equation whereas the oxidation of *ortho*-substituted benzyl alcohols with tetraparametric LDRS equation. The oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols is more susceptible to the delocalization effect than that of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds, which display a greater dependence on the field effect. The positive value of η suggests the presence of an electron-deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. The reaction is subjected to steric acceleration by the *ortho*-substituents. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Correlation analysis, halochromates, kinetics, mechanism, oxidation.

Introduction

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁵. 2,2'-Bipyridinium chlorochromate (BPCC) is also one of such compounds used as mild and selective oxidizing agent in synthetic organic chemistry⁶. We have been interested in kinetics of oxidations by Cr^{VI} species and have already published a few reports on oxidation by other pyridinium^{7,8} and quinolinium halochromates^{9,10}. In the present article we report the kinetics of oxidation of some monosubstituted benzyl alcohols by BPCC in DMSO as solvent. Attempts have been made to correlate rate and structure in this reaction.

Results and discussion

The rates and other experimental data were obtained for all the alcohols. Since the results are similar, only representative data are reproduced here.

Stoichiometry : Oxidation of benzyl alcohols by BPCC results in the oxidation of corresponding benzaldehydes. Analysis of products and the stoichiometric determinations indicate the following overall reaction (1). BPCC undergoes a two-electron change.

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order with respect to BPCC. The individual kinetic runs were strictly first order to BPCC. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was independent of initial concentration of BPCC. The reaction showed a first order dependence on the alcohol concentration (Table 1).

Induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile : The oxidation of benzyl alcohol by BPCC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen failed to induce the polymerisation of acrylonitrile (Table 1).

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence taking the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$ (Table 1). The values for a and b for benzyl alcohol are $3.26 \pm 0.06 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $5.62 \pm 0.10 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9988$).

Effect of temperature : The rates of oxidation of monosubstituted benzyl alcohols by BPCC were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2).

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by BPCC at 298 K

10^3 [BPCC] (mol dm ⁻³)	[Alcohol] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.0	0.10	0.0	5.31
1.0	0.20	0.0	10.8
1.0	0.40	0.0	21.2
1.0	0.60	0.0	31.3
1.0	0.80	0.0	42.0
1.0	1.00	0.0	52.2
2.0	0.40	0.0	22.0
4.0	0.40	0.0	21.5
6.0	0.40	0.0	22.3
8.0	0.40	0.0	21.0
1.0	0.10	0.1	6.24
1.0	0.10	0.2	7.26
1.0	0.10	0.4	9.05
1.0	0.10	0.6	10.8
1.0	0.10	0.8	12.8
1.0	0.10	1.0	14.6
1.0	0.40	0.0	22.1 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of α, α -dideuteriobenzyl alcohol was studied. Results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2).

Effect of solvents : The oxidation of benzyl alcohol was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited by the solubility of BPCC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. Kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3.

The linear correlation ($r^2 = 0.9789$) between the values of the activation enthalpies and entropies of the reaction indicated the operation of a significant compensation effect in this reaction¹¹. The reaction exhibited an excellent isokinetic effect also, as determined by Exner's method¹². Exner's plot between $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K was linear ($r^2 = 0.9991$). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the Exner's plot is 608 ± 23 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the alcohols are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in the rate are governed by changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of activation¹².

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-

independent and another acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of BPCC as (eq. 2) to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile. Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PCC¹³.

The rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) did not show any significant correlation in terms of linear solvation energy relationship of Kamlet *et al.*¹⁴. The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents (eq. 3).

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (3)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power of the solvent. C is the intercept term. ($A + B$) is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (3), separately with A and B and with ($A + B$).

$$\log k_2 = 0.62 (\pm 0.08) A + 1.59 (\pm 0.06) B - 3.82 \quad (4)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9910; \text{sd} = 0.06; n = 19; \psi = 0.15$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.39 (\pm 0.53) A - 2.73 \quad (5)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0313; \text{sd} = 0.43; n = 19; \psi = 1.01$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.54 (\pm 0.12) B - 3.61 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9039; \text{sd} = 0.13; n = 19; \psi = 0.32$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.27 \pm 0.13 (A + B) - 3.79 \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8435; \text{sd} = 0.17; n = 19; \psi = 0.21$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is Exner's statistical parameter¹⁵.

The rates of oxidation of benzyl alcohol in different solvents show an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (4) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. The solvent polarity, represented by ($A + B$), also accounted for ca. 84% of the data.

Correlation analysis of reactivity : In the late 1980s, Charton¹⁶ introduced a triparametric LDR equation for the quantitative description of structural effects on chemical reactivities. This triparametric equation results from the fact that substituent types differ in their mode of electron delocalization. This difference reflected in a different sensitivity to the electron demand for the phenomenon being studied. It has a advantage of not requiring a choice of parameters as the same three substituents con-

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by BPCC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288	298	308	318 K			
H	4.41	11.7	28.8	72.0	68.1 ± 0.6	-73 ± 2	89.7 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -Me	9.54	24.3	57.6	135	64.6 ± 0.3	-79 ± 1	87.9 ± 0.3
<i>p</i> -OMe	21.6	52.2	117	270	61.3 ± 0.6	-84 ± 2	86.0 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -F	4.54	12.2	29.9	75.6	68.5 ± 0.6	-71 ± 2	89.6 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -Cl	2.84	7.74	19.6	49.5	69.8 ± 0.4	-71 ± 1	90.8 ± 0.3
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	0.21	0.66	1.93	5.67	80.9 ± 0.7	-54 ± 2	96.8 ± 0.6
<i>p</i> -CF ₃	0.61	1.80	4.95	13.5	75.9 ± 0.5	-62 ± 2	94.4 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -COOMe	0.83	2.40	6.48	17.1	74.1 ± 0.1	-66 ± 1	93.7 ± 0.2
<i>p</i> -Br	2.78	7.60	19.2	48.6	69.9 ± 0.9	-71 ± 2	90.8 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -NHAc	10.2	25.2	60.3	144	64.6 ± 0.7	-79 ± 2	87.8 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -CN	0.37	1.13	3.20	9.00	78.3 ± 0.5	-58 ± 2	95.5 ± 0.4
<i>p</i> -SMe	12.5	31.4	72.0	171	63.5 ± 0.6	-80 ± 2	87.3 ± 0.5
<i>p</i> -NMe ₂	99.0	225	475	999	56.0 ± 0.3	-89 ± 1	82.4 ± 0.2
<i>m</i> -Me	7.56	19.6	46.8	108	64.8 ± 0.1	-86 ± 1	88.5 ± 0.1
<i>m</i> -OMe	7.20	18.4	43.5	99.9	64.1 ± 0.1	-83 ± 1	88.6 ± 0.1
<i>m</i> -Cl	1.26	3.63	9.5	25.2	71.8 ± 0.5	-65 ± 2	92.6 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -Br	1.22	3.58	9.45	24.3	73.2 ± 0.3	-66 ± 1	92.7 ± 0.2
<i>m</i> -F	1.53	4.26	11.1	28.8	71.8 ± 0.5	-69 ± 2	92.2 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	0.15	0.48	1.42	4.23	81.9 ± 0.6	-53 ± 2	97.6 ± 0.5
<i>m</i> -CO ₂ Me	0.76	2.21	6.03	16.2	75.0 ± 0.5	-64 ± 2	93.8 ± 0.4
<i>m</i> -CF ₃	0.52	1.55	4.32	11.7	76.4 ± 0.4	-62 ± 1	94.7 ± 0.3
<i>m</i> -CN	0.27	0.83	2.34	6.75	78.8 ± 0.8	-59 ± 2	96.3 ± 0.6
<i>m</i> -SMe	5.04	13.1	31.5	76.5	66.3 ± 0.4	-78 ± 1	89.5 ± 0.3
<i>m</i> -NHAc	4.50	11.9	28.8	70.2	66.9 ± 0.5	-77 ± 1	89.7 ± 0.4
<i>o</i> -Me	34.3	78.3	162	351	56.8 ± 0.6	-95 ± 2	85.1 ± 0.5
<i>o</i> -OMe	29.7	69.3	149	315	57.2 ± 0.2	-95 ± 1	85.4 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -NO ₂	0.41	1.26	3.38	9.27	76.2 ± 0.6	-65 ± 2	95.3 ± 0.5
<i>o</i> -COOMe	2.97	7.83	18.9	45.9	66.7 ± 0.4	-81 ± 1	90.7 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -NHAc	42.9	96.3	197	405	54.2 ± 0.3	-102 ± 1	84.5 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -Cl	7.61	19.1	43.5	99.9	62.6 ± 0.4	-88 ± 1	88.6 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -Br	9.81	24.1	53.8	117	60.2 ± 0.2	-94 ± 1	88.0 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -I	16.2	38.5	82.8	180	58.3 ± 0.4	-96 ± 1	86.8 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -CN	0.87	2.48	6.38	16.2	71.5 ± 0.3	-75 ± 1	93.6 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -SMe	41.3	92.7	190	387	54.1 ± 0.3	-103 ± 1	84.6 ± 0.2
<i>o</i> -F	4.75	12.5	29.7	71.1	65.9 ± 0.4	-80 ± 1	89.6 ± 0.3
<i>o</i> -CF ₃	6.03	15.1	34.2	79.2	62.5 ± 0.5	-90 ± 2	89.1 ± 0.4
α, α' -BA	0.75	2.07	5.28	13.8	71.7 ± 0.7	-77 ± 2	94.0 ± 0.5
k_H/k_D	5.88	5.65	5.45	5.22			

stants are reported to cover the range of electrical effects of the substituents. In this work we have applied the LDR eq. (8) to the rate constants, k_2 .

$$\log k_2 = L \sigma_I + D \sigma_d + R \sigma_e + h \quad (8)$$

Here, σ_I is a localized (field and/or inductive) effect

parameter, σ_d is the intrinsic delocalized electrical effect parameter when active site electronic demand is minimal and σ^* represents the sensitivity of the substituent to changes in electronic demand by the active site. The latter two substituent parameters are related by eq. (9).

$$\sigma_D = \eta\sigma_e + \sigma_d \quad (9)$$

Here η represents the electronic demand of the reaction site and is given by $\eta = R/D$, and σ_D represents the delocalized electrical parameter of the diparametric *LDR* equation.

Table 3. Solvent effect on the oxidation of benzyl alcohol by BPCC at 298 K

Solvent	$10^5 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)	Solvent	$10^5 k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)
Chloroform	41.7	Toluene	14.1
1,2-Dichloroethane	47.9	Acetophenone	91.2
Dichloromethane	39.8	Tetrahydrofuran	22.4
Dimethyl sulfoxide	117	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	17.0
Acetone	43.7	1,4-Dioxane	24.0
DMF	63.1	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	12.0
Butanone	32.4	Ethyl acetate	15.8
Nitrobenzene	51.3	Carbon disulfide	9.77
Benzene	14.8	Acetic acid	6.46
Cyclohexane	2.14		

For *ortho*-substituted compounds, it is necessary to account for the possibility of steric effects and Charton¹⁶ therefore, modified the *LDR* equation to generate the *LDRS* eq. (10).

$$\log k_2 = L\sigma_1 + D\sigma_d + R\sigma_e + Sv + h \quad (10)$$

where v is the well known Charton's steric parameter based on Van der Waals radii¹⁷.

Table 4. Temperature dependence for the reaction constants for the oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols by BPCC

<i>T/K</i>	<i>L</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>S</i>	η	<i>R</i> ₂	<i>Sd</i>	ψ	<i>P</i> _D	<i>P</i> _S
<i>para</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.61	-1.96	-1.40	-	0.71	0.9999	0.004	0.01	54.9	-
298	-1.52	-1.85	-1.32	-	0.71	0.9998	0.003	0.01	55.0	-
308	-1.43	-1.75	-1.27	-	0.73	0.9989	0.002	0.04	55.0	-
318	-1.34	-1.65	-1.18	-	0.72	0.9997	0.005	0.02	55.2	-
<i>meta</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.96	-1.33	-1.09	-	0.82	0.9998	0.006	0.01	40.4	-
298	-1.85	-1.25	-0.99	-	0.79	0.9999	0.001	0.01	40.3	-
308	-1.74	-1.17	-0.89	-	0.76	0.9989	0.003	0.04	40.2	-
318	-1.63	-1.09	-0.81	-	0.74	0.9998	0.007	0.01	40.1	-
<i>ortho</i> -Substituted										
288	-1.86	-1.61	-1.28	1.17	0.80	0.9989	0.004	0.04	46.4	25.2
298	-1.74	-1.51	-1.19	1.08	0.79	0.9999	0.001	0.01	46.5	24.9
308	-1.64	-1.42	-1.10	0.99	0.77	0.9999	0.004	0.01	46.4	24.4
318	-1.56	-1.32	-0.97	0.90	0.73	0.9998	0.007	0.02	45.8	25.2

The rates of oxidation of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols show an excellent correlation in terms of the *LDR/LDRS* equations (Table 4). We have used the standard deviation (*sd*), the coefficient of multiple determination (*R*²), and Exner's¹⁶ parameter, ψ , as the measures of goodness of fit. There is no significant co-linearity between the various substituents constants for the three series.

The comparison of the *L* and *D* values for the substituted benzyl alcohols showed that the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols is more susceptible to the delocalization effect than to the localized effect. However, the oxidation of *ortho*- and *meta*-substituted compounds exhibited a greater dependence on the field effect. In all the cases, the magnitude of the reaction constants decreases with an increase in the temperature, pointing to a decrease in selectivity with an increase in temperature.

All three regression coefficients, *L*, *D* and *R*, are negative indicating an electron-deficient carbon centre in the activated complex for the rate-determining step. The positive value of η adds a negative increment to σ_d , reflecting the electron-donating power of the substituent and its capacity to stabilise a cationic species. The positive value of *S* indicates that the reaction is subject to steric acceleration by an *ortho*-substituent.

The percent contribution¹⁷ of the delocalized effect, *P*_D, is given by eq. (11).

$$P_D = (|D| \times 100) / (|L| + |D|) \quad (11)$$

Similarly, the percent contribution of the steric parameter¹⁷ to the total effect of the substituent, *P*_S, was determined by using eq. (12).

$$P_S = (|S| \times 100) / (|L| + |D| + |S|) \quad (12)$$

The values of *P*_D and *P*_S are also recorded in Table 4. The value of *P*_D for the oxidation of *para*-substituted benzyl alcohols is *ca.* 55% whereas the corresponding values for the *meta*- and *ortho*-substituted alcohols are *ca.* 40 and 46% respectively. This shows that the balance of localization and delocalization effects is different for differently substituted benzyl alcohols. The less pronounced resonance effect from the *ortho*-position than from the *para*-position may be due to the twisting away of the alcoholic group from the plane of the benzene ring. The magnitude of the *P*_S value shows that the steric effect is significant in this reaction.

The positive value of *S* showed a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis high ground state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product aldehyde as

well as the transition state leading to it, the transition state energy of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore results.

Mechanism :

A hydrogen abstraction mechanism leading to the formation of the free radicals is unlikely in view of the failure to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile and no effect of the radical scavenger on the reaction rate. The presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of a α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The negative values of the localization and delocalization electrical effects i.e. of *L*, *D* and *R* points to an electron-deficient reaction centre in the rate-determining step. It is further supported by the positive value of η , which indicates that the substituent is better able to stabilise a cationic or electron-deficient reactive site. Therefore, a hydride-ion transfer in the rate-determining step is suggested. The hydride-ion transfer mechanism is also supported by the major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents. The hydride ion transfer may take place either by a cyclic process via an ester intermediate or by an acyclic one-step bimolecular process. Kwart and Nickle¹⁸ have shown that a dependence of kinetic isotope effect on temperature can be gainfully employed to determine whether the loss of hydrogen proceeds through a concerted cyclic process or by an acyclic one. The data for protio- and deuterio-benzyl alcohols, fitted to the familiar expression : $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D (-\Delta H^*/RT)$ ^{19,20} show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state in which activation energy difference for protio and deuterio compounds is equal to the difference in the zero-point energy for the respective C-H and C-D bonds ($\approx 4.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are almost equal. Similar phenomena were observed earlier in the oxidation of alcohols by PCC⁷ and QFC¹⁰. Therefore in the present studies the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic bimolecular process. It is well-established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterised by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer²¹. Littler²² has also shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxidation of alcohols by Cr^{VI}, involves six electrons and, being a Hückel-type system, is an allowed process. Thus, a transition state having a planar, cyclic and symmetrical structure can be envisaged for the decomposition of the ester intermediate. Hence, the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and

then a decomposition of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Schemes 1 and 2). The proposed mechanism leads to the following rate-laws, which in conformity with the experimental data.

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 K_2 [\text{BPCC}] [\text{alcohol}] + K_1 K_3 k_2 [\text{BPCC}] [\text{alcohol}] [\text{H}^+].$$

Acid-independent path

Scheme 1

Acid-dependent path

Scheme 2

Materials and methods :

BPCC was prepared by the reported method⁶ and its purity checked by an iodometric method. The procedure used for the purification of alcohols has been described earlier²³. α, α -Dideuteriobenzyl alcohol (PhCH_2OH) was prepared by the reported method²⁴. Its isotopic purity, as ascertained by its NMR spectra, was $95 \pm 4\%$. Due to non-aqueous nature of the solvent, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Solvents were purified by the usual methods²⁵.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, benzyl alcohol (5.4 g, 0.05 mol) and BPCC (3.10 g, 0.01 mol) were made up to 50 cm³ in DMSO and kept in the dark for *ca.* 15 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 cm³) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol, and weighed again. The yields of DNP before and after recrystallization were 2.65 g (93%) and 2.20 g (78%) respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of benzaldehyde. The IR spectra of the isolated DNP and an authentic sample were superimposable. This confirmed the identity of the product. Similar experiments were performed with other alcohols also. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures, determined by an iodometric method was 3.95 ± 0.10 .

Kinetic measurements : The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or more) of the alcohol over BPCC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (± 0.1 K), by monitoring the decrease in [BPCC] spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990 - 0.999$) plots of log [BPCC] against time for up to 80% reaction. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was obtained from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}} / [\text{alcohol}]$.

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